

CODE MIXING IN STUDENTS' TWITTER STATUS AT SULTAN AGENG TIRTAYASA UNIVERSITY IN BANTEN, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

This study is intended to find out (1) why do the students use code mixing in their communication at twitter status (2) what factors influence the students in using code mixing in twitter status (3) what types of code mixing that students produce in their status. The technique used is qualitative research through content analysis. The data were gathered by doing observation, documentation, and interview. Researchers focused on code mixing used by students at Eighth Semester of Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa University. To analyze data, the researchers used matrix descriptive of Miles and Huberman consisted of data reduction, data display, and drawing conclusion/verification. Data reduction was used to collect data from observation, documentation, and interview. Last, conclusion was used to describe all of the data. The result of this research was form of code mixing used by the students, including insertation, alternation, congruent lexicalization. Then, the factors cause code mixing due to the psychological factors from the students.

Keywords: code mixing, insertion, alternation, congruent lexicalization, matrix descriptive

1. Introduction

The issue of multinational era becomes a crucial topic to be discussed since Indonesian is one of multilingual or bilingual society, so one should have a competency to speak using another language beside first language. Lack of access to bilingual education is

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one of the factors that may lead to poverty (Danbolt, 2011). How we can communicate our ideas in different language and culture? We know that we acquire the language consciously and unconsciously. Both from the environment around us and formal education like in school. All aspects of ourselves are affected as we struggle to reach beyond the confines of our first language and to enter into a new language, culture, and the way of thinking, feeling, and acting. Total commitment, involvement, physical, intellectual, and emotional responds are necessary to able to successfully send a receive message in a foreign language. So that's why, we need to learn the language formally, to have an ability in speaking fluently to every people in this bilingual or multilingual world. The fact that bilingualism and biculturalism have become accepted as major goals in school as an important advance, but if these goals are to be achieved, at least some understanding of the nature of code alternation and its meaning in everyday interaction is required. Bilingualism is after all primarily a linguistic term refereeing to the fact that linguists have discovered significant alternations in phonology, morphology, and syntax in studying verbal behavior of a particular population. While bilingual phenomena have certain linguistic features, the occurrence of these themselves may have quite different social significance (Gumperz, 1972:186).

Language behavior has gains a great deal of attention among social scientists and educators because it raises several important questions among them: Which language is use-where, when, among whom and why? To what norms of inter action and interpretation should its use be subject? Questions have also been asked about how community and personal beliefs, values, and practices impose upon the acquisition and use of language by children as well as adults. The accepted paradigm nowadays or the linguistic study of bilingualism is the code switching and code mixing paradigm. Having observed that linguistic alternant exists at the level of phonology and syntax, the next step is to ask what alternant is used, when and under what circumstances. The assumptions are that behavior can be analyzed according to distinct social occasions, interaction, sequences, or speech events. These events are then assumed to be associated with culturally specific behavior norm which, in turn, determine the speech forms to be used. To some extent, this indeed is the case (Gumperz, 1972:190).

Code-switching is the alternation between two codes (languages or dialects), between people who share those particular codes. Choices about how code switching manifests itself are determined by a number of social and linguistic factors. It is quite typical in multicultural and immigrant populations. Code-switching can take on several forms including alteration of sentences; phrases form both languages, and switching in along narrative. In normal conversations between two bilingualisms, code-switching consists of eighty-four percent single word switches, ten percent phrase switches, and

six percent clause switching (Skiba, 1997, para. 2). Hence, the researcher defined code switching as the alternate use of two or more languages in the same utterance or conversation, as in these three examples:

1. An Indonesian-English bilingual speaking Bahasa Indonesia and switching (words in an Indonesian) to English (From status in the twitter): Henry June @henryjune: *"Shopping sebutir pear saja cukup"*
2. An Indonesian speaking bahasa Indonesia and switching to English (From status in the twitter): itzmeMunaw @nawmu_naw: *"Lagi banyak waktu luang tapi tetep gak ngerjain tugas lebih awal."* So, who is the trouble maker in your life?
3. An Indonesian speaking bahasa Indonesia and switching to English: Ayu Febriani A @mmmmmpu: *"Belum cuci muka dari tadi siang. Males banget bawaannya"*. How lazy I am.

From these three examples, we see that code switching could involve a word (shopping in example 1), a phrase (So, who is the trouble maker in your life? In example 2), or a sentence (How lazy I am, in example 3). It can also involve several sentences. What is important is that switching is different from borrowing a word from the other language and integrating it phonologically and morphologically into the based language. In code switching, the switched element is not integrated; instead, there is a total shift to the other language.

The other kind of bilingualism paradigm is code mixing. Code-mixing is the change of one language to another within the same utterance or in the same oral/written text. It is a common phenomenon in societies in which two or more languages are used. Studies of code-mixing enhance our understanding of the nature, process and constraints of language (Myers-Scotton, 1993a; Boeschoten 1998; Azuma, 1998), and of the relationship between language use and individual values, communicative strategies, language attitudes and functions within particular socio-cultural contexts. (Auer, 1998; Jacobson, 1998; Myers-Scotton, 1993b; Ludi, 2003).

In code mixing, there is necessarily a base language and it should be possible to distinguish in an utterance monolingual chunks in the base language which alternate with chunks calling upon the rules of both languages. For example, in Indonesian (a mixed bahasa Indonesia-English) *"Mau lunch dimana nih?"* is an Indonesian sentence comprising a Indonesian phrasal verb *"Mau makan siang dimana nih?"* and an English morpheme "lunch", which is prepositioned to the verb according to an Indonesian rule unacceptable in English. It was of course possible to observe these two phenomena within a single utterance, in which case code mixing could be embedded in code switching, but not the reverse. Note that the distinction between the two is not absolute

and there are utterances which can be classified in either category. Note also that code mixing can trigger off code switching (Clyne, 1967; Kachru, 1982).

The phenomenon above is a proof that we live in multinational era, wherever we live, whenever we stay we should adapt ourselves to the new environment. Here, the researcher found a case that happen in Indonesian, that is the using of code mixing in Twitter social media because the using of code mixing in Twitter status can be used as the teaching media in teaching and learning process to make students' fluently in conveying information, because we know that Twitter is the most popular social media in this world especially in Indonesia and most of the viewer is student. All people know Twitter, so, why the students not use only one language. Why they should do the code mixing in the status. All the questions were the reason why the researcher was interesting to observe or investigate this case study of code mixing that happens in Twitter.

2. Literature Review

Code is a system that is used by people to communicate with each other. When people went to talk each other, they have to choose a particular code to express their feeling. According to Myers-Scotton (1998) cited in Coulmas (2005:110) states that a code in this sense can be a language or variety of a language. In additional, Stockwell (2002:8) says that a code is used by people to speak or communicate in a particular language, or dialect, or register, or accent, or style on different occasions and for different purposes. Similarly, Wardaugh (1986:101) also maintains that a code can be defined as a system used for communication between two or more parties used on any occasions. When two or more people communicate with each other in speech, we can call the system of communication that they employ a code. Therefore, people are usually required to select a particular code whenever they choose to speak, and they may also decide to switch from one code to another or mix codes, sometimes in every short utterances and it means to create a code

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The definition of code mixing given by Bokamba (1988: 21-62), for instance, is devoid of sociolinguistic considerations; for him code mixing coincides with intra sentential code switching. Code mixing in this definition seems to be exactly the kind of linguistic behavior "ideal bilingual" is not supposed to practice. Code mixing occurs when conversant use both language together to the extent that they change from one language to the other in the course of a single utterance.

There is continuum between code switching and code mixing. Code mixing, like code switching, is a language contact communication strategy, but the speaker of language, L_x, transfers elements or rules of another language, L_y, to L_x at all linguistic level of L_x, otherwise they would be considered as loans (in other words, code mixing, like uninterrupted transfers or nonce-words, is a phenomenon of 'parole' not language;).

In code switching there is necessarily a base language and it should be possible to distinguish in an utterance monolingual chunks in the base language which alternate with chunks calling upon the rules of both languages. For example, in Indonesian (a mixed Bahasa Indonesia- English) "*mau lunch dimana nih?*" is Indonesian sentence comprising an Indonesian phrasal verb "*mau makan siang di mana nih?*" and English morpheme 'lunch', which is prepositioned to the verb according to an Indonesian rule unacceptable in English. It is of course possible to observe these two phenomena within a single utterance, in which case code mixing can be embedded in code switching, but not the reverse. Note that the distinction between the two phenomena is not absolute and there are utterances which can be classified in either category. Note also that code mixing can trigger off code switching (Clyne, 1967; Kachru, 1982).

Therefore, that it is not always easy to distinguish code mixing from code switching. Like code switching, code mixing is a strategy of bilingual speaker. (whereas borrowing is not), in the sense that it is a fact of language, and monolinguals can make use of it. Code mixing can of course express a lack of competence in the base language, such as lexical items, and in this case, code mixing can compensate for this deficiently. However, as for code switching, code mixing can be a bilingual's specific code which enables him to express attitudes, intentions, roles, and to identify with a particular group.

3. Types of Code Mixing

Muyskin (2000) suggests that there are three main code-mixing patterns which may be found in bilingual speech communities: insertion, alternation, and congruent lexicalization. One pattern will usually dominate, though not necessarily to the

exclusion of other patterns Muyskin's view of the relation between code mixing patterns and extra linguistic factors. Code mixing pattern Linguistic factors favoring these pattern extra linguistic factors favoring this pattern. Insertion Typological distance Colonial settings recount migrant communicates asymmetry in speaker's proficiency in two languages. Alternation Typological Distance Stable bilingual community's tradition of language separation. Congruent lexicalization Typological similar language Two language has roughly equal prestige no tradition of overt language separation.

a. Insertional code mixing

In the insertional pattern, one language determines the overall structure into which constituents from the other language are inserted: this is illustrated in Figure 1 based on Muysken (2000:7).

This pattern is assumed by the matrix language frame (MLF) theory proposed by Myers-Scotton (e.g. 1993).it can be illustrated by Swahili-English example from Myers-Scotton (1993:86):

"A-na-ku-l-a plate M-bili z-murram"

'He eats two plates of maize'

In this example, the word order is as in swahili, including the phrase *plate m-bili* "two plates", and all inflectional morphology is from swahili. The asymmetry between the languages involved in the insertional pattern is captured in the MLF by labeling the main language the "matrix" language and the other the "embedded" language. The example of insertion (Indonesian-English) was also can be seen in an article entitled "code switching and code mixing in Internet Chatting: between 'yes', 'ya', and 'si' a case study' written by neni Isharyanti (2009).

B: *"tergantung team, juga tergantung event."* (it is depending on the team and on the event.)

b. Alternational code mixing

In alternation pattern, both languages occur alternately each with their structure. It constraints on mixing in terms of the comp ability or equivalence of the languages involved at the switch point. It seems that halfway through the sentence, one language is replaced by the other. As illustrated in figure 2 based on Myusken (2000:7).

This type of code-mixing is assumed in poplack's work (e.g. 1980) and is well represented in her data in examples like (poplack: 1980:589):

("why make Carol sentarse atras pa' que everybody has to move pa' que se salga?")

"Why make carol sit in the back so that everybody has to move for her to get out?"

In this example, each language stretch, English or Spanish, has its own language specific syntax and morphology. The example of alternation (Indonesian-English) was also can be seen in an article entitled "code switching and code mixing in Internet Chatting: between 'yes', 'ya', and 'si' a case study' written by neni Isharyanti (2009).

B: *"I mean, ganti pake kata lain."*

(I mean, change it to another sentence.)

c. Congruent Lexicalization code mixing

Congruent lexicalization mixes lexical material from different the usage occurs in a shared grammatical structure. *"the grammatical structure is shared by languages A and b, and words from both languages a and b are inserted more or less randomly"* (Muysken 2000:8). This is illustrated in figure 3 based on Muysken (200:8).

The example of congruent lexicalization (Indonesian-English) was also can be seen in an article entitled "code switching and code mixing in Internet Chatting: between 'yes', 'ya', and 'si' a case study' written by neni Isharyanti (2009).

B: *"software gua buat convert file wav jadi mp3 gua udah expired."*

(my software for converting wav files to mp3s has expired.)

4. Method

In this research, the researcher conducts a qualitative research. According to Bogdan & Biklen that one of the characteristics of qualitative research is to have the nature setting as direct source of data and the researcher is the key of the instrument (1982:27). The researcher used qualitative research. This research explained and identified the phenomena of research subject by collecting, identifying, describing, classifying, and evaluating. Considering the method of the research above, the researcher determined research design to get data by using non-experimental design. So, the researcher only observed and described the result of data collecting. The researcher used the analysis for the title of the research, because in analyzing the researcher investigated a person or a social unit deeply. The researcher found all the important variables in the developmental the subject itself and then the researcher captured it.

5. Research Subject

This research subject was the status in Twitter social media. The researcher was interested in the using of code mixing in student's status of Twitter. The researcher observed the way students provides their status in Twitter social media. Source of data

in this research was Twitter social media status. The researcher wanted to know about the using of code mixing that usually doing by ten of 8th semester students.

6. Instruments

The instrument of this research was the researcher itself as observer, planner, and actor in collecting the data, and analyzing the data. According to Guba and Lincoln (1981:128-150), there are common characteristics of human as the instrument of research. They are:

1. Responsive, human as the responsive instrument toward the environment and toward the people around the environment itself interactively.
2. Adaptable, human as the instrument can adapt himself/herself to many people and situation.
3. Emphasize to totality, human as the instrument use their imagination and their creativity and look at this world as a totality.
4. Basic knowledge, human has mind to think and to show up their ideas; with it human can get so many knowledge as the basic to do a research.
5. Processing data quickly; another skill that has by the human is processing data quickly after the data collected, rearrange the data, and change the inquiry of the research.
6. Clarification and summarization; human as an ability to explain or clarify something to the subject or respondent which is have not understand something yet about the research that the researcher do.
7. Find the idiosyncratic response; human as ability to find something new and it is really needed in conduct the research.

Therefore, the researcher became the instrument in her own research to investigate about a case study in code mixing that happen in student's status of twitter social media. In conducted the research, the researcher used photograph as the data documentation, tape script of twitter status to record the result of the interview.

7. Result and Discussion

In conducting the observation, the researcher observed in twitter status. The researcher monitored the twitter during one month when the researcher found code mixing in student's twitter account, the researcher captured it. The research knew that most of students prefer to use alternation, the second is insertion and the last one is congruent

lexicalization. Most of the students used code mixing in that twitter to emphasize what they wanted to say. For example: *"tentang apa enaknyaaaa. Any request?"*. Table 1 (2)

The students asked a suggestion to her follower, first she asked it in Bahasa then mixed it with English as the emphasizing phrase. Another example in the following example: *"so hungry ✎ ga sempet sarapan:"* Table 1 (16)

In this example, she used English phrase then mixed it with Bahasa. The phrase "so hungry" here means about her feeling of something that she has not done.

Another reason why the students used code mixing in their twitter status because they want to give intention of the speech content for example: *"Love itu cinta. Miss itu kangen"*. Table 1 (1)

In the worlds love and miss, the students want to deliver the real meaning in Bahasa. Most of the reason why the students used code mixing in their twitter status is to express group identity. Here, the researcher took the data from eighth semester in English semester in English Department Students that's why they have a habit to use English in daily communication. For example: *"I have no special feelings except that besties feels but why he treats me like this?"*. *"Apa efek lama ga ketemu?"*. Table 1 (4)

This example proof that the students usually used code mixing in her daily communication. People consider that language is the most important means of communication in human life. It is used to interact with other and to convey some information. By using language, people can express ideas, experiences, thoughts, wants hopes, feeling and so on to other. The accurate of the uses of language can deliver the real meaning of language itself and the purpose of language also can be delivered well. Language develops and has many changed and variation, depending on its influence. It means that language varieties can be found not only in informal situation but also in formal situation based on the needs. Language societies are bilinguals and multilinguals.

Indonesia has Indonesian language or Bahasa as national language and many vernacular or regional languages, but Indonesia also has English as a foreign language. Indonesia who does not use vernacular language as their first language, they use Bahasa as their first language and they may use vernacular as their second language, but Indonesian societies still learn English as a foreign language. It means, in daily activity they speak more than one language. This reality also occurs when they are study in the school, include in learning English.

When bilinguals are communicating, or interacting with others, they may use code-mixing. It is the process of using two languages by people that consists of the native language and the second or foreign language. According to Muysken (2000: 1) defines that code-mixing as all cases where lexical items and grammatical features from

two languages appear in one sentence. One of the phenomenon in mixing the language is in twitter we can see many people use English in their status. The researcher found several students of English Department use code mixing in their status that is why the researcher used them to take the data.

The researcher had already taken the data from an English student at eighth semester English Department students of Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa University. Moreover, the students during 8 times (June 1st, June 2nd, June 8th, June 9th, June 15th, June 16th, June 22nd, June 23rd, 2013) had been used as the research subject. In this research, the researcher focused to analysis code mixing used by the students when they were updating status. They have done observation to describe how the students used code mixing in twitter social media. The researcher did it to know more deeply about code mixing used by the students.

A. June 1st, 2013

a. Insertion:

- *"Udah lah yah. No time to remember you. Bergegas, semangaaaaatt...."*
- *"Good luck for my dad, mudah-mudahan lancer, dipermudah dan lulus yah ... Amiin God bless you ..."*
- *"Aah typo mulu gagal deh"*
- *"Ampun deh ujannya aweetttt ga move on move on #ganyambung"*
- *"Celebrating TVXQ members' bday together every year, meski Cuma lewat twitter but I'm happy, really." Simple but meaningful.*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

b. Alteration:

- *"The power of kepepet. Hiyaaaaaaa!!!!!"*
- *"Quality time watching fast furious 6 with kekasih hati ~"*
- *"Have u ever feel like u wanna cry but u are not allowed to do that? Alloh, tolong kuatkan dia"*
- *"Is it my tweetdeck or the signal?? Lambat banget..."*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students just wanted to inform that they want to say in English.

- *"I'll inform later. Masih nyari info juga."*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

B. June 2nd, 2013

a. Insertion:

- *"The weather is truly hot. Iya, hot kayak gue: D"*
- *"Init uh udh yg the best I can do looh"*
- *"Lupa sama diet. Ate too much as my late dinner *nyesel*"*
- *"I've proved that ga usah capek2 bls kejahatan org... Cman nmbah june 2nd, 2013 dosa aja. Allah has fully right for doing that for you."*
- *"Woyaaaa ... minggu malem ... Monday sickness nya dah kerasa banget emang hhhhaaaaa"*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

b. Alteration:

- *"I have no special feelings expect that 'besties' feels but why he treats me like this? Ga biasanya banget. Apa efek lama ga ketemu?"*
- *"Really, wanna have Brian's car at Fast Furious 6 movie. Merah, mahal. Menantang"*
- *"Wah banyak moment kereeen disana, can't wait someone to uploading pic and video."*

c. Congruent Lexicalization

- *"Ga ngerayain Saturday night itu bukan masalah besar koq, coz masih ada Sunday night, Monday night dll... seneng'y sama aja tuh...."*

This example, it can be interpreted that the students used familiar word in English.

- *"Seriously pengen ke lampung. Ngebayangin gue di bus duduk nikmatin perjalanan ke kruki sore sore gini bikin gue bad mood."*

C. June 8th, 2013

a. Insertion

- *"Lagi ditutorin "Wedding Preparation" sama calon mantan"*
- *"Abis nge stalking akunya mantan."*
- *"Bang lu kereeen bgt bikin ginian, bikin bljr English more be fun salut sumpah"✌"*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

b. Alternation

- *"Kapan lulus? Sorry, I have no time to explain, and you won't care about it either."*

This example, it can be interpreted that the students used familiar word in English.

- *"Oh can't wait. Semoga ga ujan deh siang ini."*

This example, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

- *"First time ke Oriflame Sudirman di Menara Standard Chartered kemarin sendirian ahahah"*

These example (first time), it can be interpreted that the students used familiar words and (standard chartered) is name of place.

- *"Love itu cinta. Miss itu cinta."*
- *"Oke ini efek lama ga ketemu but I admit dia jadi more gentle sekarang. Alhamdulillah manner nya bagus."*

This example, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

- *"Katanya serang lagi so shine like a diamond ya? Tangerang all day long mendung dan sekalang lagi rainy nih, so cold: D"*

This example, it can be interpreted that the students used familiar word in English.

- *"Muka lo PERFECT, tapi hati lo PER FUCK!"*

This example, it can be interpreted that the students used familiar word in English.

D. June 9th, 2013

a. Insertion

- *"Yang Wonderful world tuh asik juga (buat ngegalau sih) hahaha"*
- *"Thanks berat ya buat kultwinty smalem... amazing! :D"*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

b. Alternation

- *"Got advisors' signature already but dont know isi skripshit sendiri itu.. agak ..gimana.. gitu.."*
- *"Still unbelieving with these advisors' signature. Ya Allah, Alhamdulillah.. Ga nyangka.."*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to inform what they want to say in English.

- *:First time lho yah liat banjir - _____ -"*
- *"Waaaaw temen udah wisuda aja. happy graduation"*
- *"Minum cucu'y Udah, and now time to sleep (=| "*

- *"aaaaa you get me wrong. Bukan itu maksudnya"*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

c. Congruent Lexicalization

- *"segini matahari udah mahal department store apa lagi yg more expensive kaya Debenhams? wajar aja it is United Kingdom's Brands"*

This example (department store), it can be interpreted that the student said name of place in English. On the other hand, (more expensive) the student used familiar word. And then (United Kingdom's brands) the students said brand for some stuffs.

- *"udah H-1 tapi bigdaddy blm confirm siapa second guest nya"* (this example, it can be interpreted that the student used familiar words in English.

E. June 15th, 2013

a. Insertion

- *"Folder di notebook: pacar sampe mei" dan alhamdulillah tercapai... sisa bulannya tgl doing research+analyze data. Semangat!"*
- *"Gue angel of death, siap2 gue cabut nyawa dari samping"*
- *"Lg flashback msa2 kkm"*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel comfortable with it.

b. Alternation

- *"tentang apa enaknyaaaa. Any request?"*
- *"This example, it can be interpreted that the student asked to the followers to make sure."*
- *"A friend of mine said that she cannot read the examiner's handwriting.... perlu ke arkeolog sepertinya :!"*
- *"SelamaT Hari Tembakauu bUat para lelaki, especially for my boyfriend. #dont love it too much, just love me so much<="*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wants to inform what they want to say in English.

- *"karaokean two hours only yah"*
- *"So hungry :((gak sempet sarapan"*
- *"melangkah dg pasti.. berikhtiar sudah psti, dg doa tnpa henti. berharap sang ilahi mengabulkan keinginan hati.. #bismillah pray for tomorrow"*
- *"Wah udah sampe yah, welcome to Indonesia bro"*

This example, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

F. June 16th, 2013

a. Insertion

- *"goodnite people...gonna sleep earlier now for a better tomorrow, cu tomorrow at Gedung Al-Azhar (gtw ruang brpa: D) ... *bye"*

This example, it can be interpreted that the student wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

b. Alternation

- *"so sweet deh, ngerti bgt gmn yg aku rasain. jd terharu. Hehehe xD"*
- *"Dibales disangka ngerespon; ga dibales dibilang sombong. What should I do then????"*
- *"On the way back home. Macet sekali -, -"*
- *"salamin ya buat.. sorry couldn't come :("*
- *"wish an awesome birthday. Cpet peneitian+sidang, Lulus tahun ini deh, amien"*
- *"Seneeng liat pada kumpul, safe flight yaah :)"*
- *"Ya ampun I'm about to crazy!"*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

c. Congruent Lexicalization

- *"paling seneng ngasih2 something ke mama, langsung dijajalin. she knows how to appreciate :)"*

This example (something), it can be interpreted that the student used familiar word. On the other hand, (she knows how to appreciate) the student showed express her feeling.

- *"Prepare!! Besok berangkat'y jam 7. Ga boleh da yg ketinggalan. Handphone paling penting, hha"*

This example, it can be interpreted that the student used familiar words.

G. June 22nd, 2013

a. Insertion

- *"pokoknya mah I LOVE SKRIPSI SOOOOO MUCH!!! *cium skripsi :p"*
- *"Iya deh lain kali ga next time lagi... Serious ini mahhhh.... ☹"*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

b. Alternation

- *"If only I knew them earlier ah~ 15 years clearly aint a short time. Many things happened. Susah nyarinya.."*

This example, it can be interpreted that the student wanted to inform what they want to say in English.

- *"Wish you were here, doa dari tadi siang sih"*
- *"Gapapa lah tanda tangan gak dapet. Bisa nyari buah tangan :) let's gooooo :D"*
- *"So tired. Undangan ampe setengah hari gini"*
- *"Attending seminar. masih ngantook."*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

- *"great! syukur dh klo bgus"*

This example, it can be interpreted that the student used familiar word.

c. Congruent Lexicalization

- *"pngen bgt rasanya ngirim sms-blast ke dospem yg isinya *tahnk you so much mam*... masih ga nyangka ya Allah iniiiih.."*

This example (blast), it can be interpreted that the student used familiar word. On the other hand, (thank you so much mam) the student showed express her feeling.

- *"Absurd amat iklan happy call pake lagu big bang:|"*

This example (absurd), it can be interpreted that the student used familiar word. (happy call) the student said a brand of kitchen stuff.

H. June 23rd, 2013

a. Insertion

- *"KKM itu unforgettable moment banget."*
- *"Precious time itu masak+ makan bareng with my Mom and my sisters."*
- *"Aduuuuh terharu bgt dpt blsan sms dr dospem gue itu... Really gald for having your mam as my advisor. *nangis bahagia*"*
- *"Don't be galau sist: D"*
- *"katanya: further notice would be given. Ya ampun berasa ngomong sama detektif."*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

b. Alternation

- *"I should re-check my ppt presentation for Monday tapi pcnya dipake babeh -_-"*
- *"makin bersyukur makin diberi lebih... thats more tahn enough, thats more than me. :))"*

From these examples, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to inform what they want to say in English.

- *"Random lah ini malam :("*

This example, it can be interpreted that the students wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it.

c. Congruent Lexicalization

- *"get dressed rapih pake rok and jilbab gede ternyata aman jam segini, malah dimuliain sama kaum pria. Thanks God."*

This example (get dressed, and), it can be interpreted that the student used familiar word. On the other hand, (thanks God) the student showed express her feeling.

- *"tp yg gw suka iklan cigarette yg tagline nya 'Act Now!'... sounds nice... hho"*

This example, it can be interpreted that the student used familiar word.

Furthermore, after observing and analyzing the whole data, the researcher found retypes of code mixing by Muysken presented of this research. The types by Muysken included in code mixing used by the students were: (1) the Insertion Pattern, (2) the Alternation Pattern, (3) The Congruent Lexicalization Pattern.

In insertion, the students mix a word or phrase in a sentence. In alternation code mixing in the first sentence start by English word or phrase and follow by Bahasa word or phrase. In congruent lexicalization the students used more than one word or phrase. Related to the use of language all of the students were studying in English Department. So, it became a habit for them to use English in their daily communication. Even they did not speak English 100% but they tried to implement it in their communication. Besides that, when they wanted to use full English in their status, it would make their other friend difficult to understand what they wanted to say.

Code mixing occurred in teaching in learning process was to help the students easier in comprehending and improving their vocabulary. Unconsciously, made a status in English helped the students in teaching learning process. In accordance with the result of the research, it could be found that English usage in making status at eighth semester English Department students of Sultan Ageng Tirtayasa University only in some parts of the activities in implementing English. The students use English when they were emphasizing sentence. Related the result of the students eighth semester, the researcher got three types of code mixing based on Muysken theory occurred in the status: insertion, alternation and congruent lexicalization. The reasons why the students used insertion, alternation and congruent lexicalization it can be interpreted that the student wanted to emphasize what they want to say in English they prefer use English to be mixed with Bahasa because they feel more comfortable with it. Further, from the

observation and interview, it could be summarized which is from one factor causing for code mixing applied by the students, i.e.: comfortable factor. It is supported by several reasons, such as: the phenomenon, the advantages to used code mixing is to make their English language more fluently and improve their vocabulary, there is no special time to make code mixing status, they make it whenever they want, and the last one, they use code mixing in their daily conversation to improve their English language.

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